

Thermodynamic Study of Chelation of Rare Earth(III) Ions with 2,3-Dihydroxynaphthalene (DON)

B. C. BHUYAN and S. N. DUBEY*

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-132 119 (Haryana)

Manuscript received 12 December 1979, revised 29 July 1980, accepted 7 August 1980

The chelation of 2, 3-dihydroxynaphthalene with trivalent La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho and Y have been studied pH-metrically at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ in aqueous ethanol (10% v/v) at different ionic concentrations (0.05, 0.1, 0.15 and 0.2M KNO_3). Formation of 1 : 1 chelates are indicated. The order of stability is found to be

The thermodynamic stability constants and free energies of chelation have been reported.

ALTHOUGH the complexes of 2, 3-dihydroxynaphthalene-6-sulphonic acid with rare earth(III) ions have been studied¹ potentiometrically, the literature for 2, 3-dihydroxynaphthalene complexes are scanty. Poluektov *et al*² have studied the stability of mixed ligand chelates of trivalent rare earths using DON as one of the ligands. In view of the above, our present work deals with the potentiometric study of chelation of trivalent La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho and Y with 2, 3-dihydroxynaphthalene at different ionic concentrations (0.05, 0.1, 0.15 and 0.2M KNO_3) in aqueous ethanol (10% v/v) at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ using Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique^{3,4} as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁵.

Experimental

The rare earth nitrates (Indian Rare Earth Ltd.) were dissolved in double distilled water and standardized by standard method⁶. All other reagents used were of AR grade and the solutions were prepared in boiled out doubly distilled water. Considering the low solubility of 2, 3-dihydroxynaphthalene in cold water under the experimental

conditions, the solutions were prepared in aqueous ethanol (10% v/v).

A Philips pH-meter (PR 9405M) with glass and calomel electrodes was used for measuring the pH. The experimental details have been discussed in previous communications from this laboratory⁷. The titrations were performed in duplicates and the results found to be reproducible.

Results and Discussion

The formation functions \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL were calculated from the standard equations^{8,9}. The observed pH meter readings were the same in water and aqueous ethanol mixture (10% v/v) for acid, ligand and metal titrations, thus eliminating the correction of the pH values. The proton-ligand stability constants were determined at different ionic concentrations (0.5, 0.1, 0.15 and 0.2M) and the values were computed by (1) interpolation at half \bar{n} values, (2) pointwise calculation method, (3) correction term method⁹ and (4) curve fitting method¹⁰. The mean values are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC STABILITY CONSTANTS AND FREE ENERGIES OF CHELATION OF RARE EARTH(III) IONS WITH 2,3-DIHYDROXYNAPHTHALENE AT 30°C

Metal ions	Constants	$\mu=0.0M$	$\mu=0.05M$	$\mu=0.1M$	$\mu=0.15M$	$\mu=0.2M$	$-\Delta G \text{ kJ mole}^{-1}$
H ⁺	$\log K_1^H$	12.57	12.41	12.36	12.25	12.19	72.950
	$\log K_2^H$	9.10	9.01	8.95	8.92	8.85	52.810
La ³⁺	$\log K_1$	10.86	10.52	10.32	9.93	9.30	63.039
Pr ³⁺	$\log K_1$	11.40	11.01	10.60	10.34	9.95	66.172
Nd ³⁺	$\log K_1$	11.50	11.09	10.72	10.42	10.16	66.754
Sm ³⁺	$\log K_1$	12.13	11.55	11.22	10.84	10.70	70.411
Gd ³⁺	$\log K_1$	12.15	11.76	11.27	11.07	10.76	70.527
Tb ³⁺	$\log K_1$	12.60	11.98	11.66	11.37	11.10	73.139
Dy ³⁺	$\log K_1$	13.02	12.44	11.83	11.64	11.24	75.577
Ho ³⁺	$\log K_1$	13.20	12.68	12.29	11.83	11.54	76.622
Y ³⁺	$\log K_1$	12.25	11.78	11.54	11.21	10.98	71.107

* To whom correspondence should be addressed.

The metal ligand formation curves obtained by plotting \bar{n} versus pL showed that the values of \bar{n} vary between 0.1 and 0.9, thereby indicating the formation of only 1 : 1 complex in these systems. Above $\bar{n} \approx 0.9$, precipitation of the complexes starts, which disappears at $pH \approx 11$. The pL values were computed by using the above computational techniques (except Correction Term method) and the mean values are tabulated in Table 1.

Thermodynamic stability constants were calculated by plotting $\log K_1$ values against μ and extrapolating to zero ionic concentration. $\log K_1^{\mu=0}$ values were plotted against ionic radii (r^{-1}) (Fig. 1). The stability increases with decrease in ionic radii, as expected, with a slight break at or near Gd^{3+} ion. The break near Gd^{3+} ion may be interpreted as corresponding to either the stability of half filled ($4f^7$) arrangement of Gd^{3+} ion or the changes in ionic radii¹¹ centering at the Gd^{3+} ion which allows a change in coordination number of the cations.

Fig. 1. Plot of Thermodynamic Stability Constants ($\log K_1^{\mu=0}$) versus Ionic radii (r^{-1}).

The free energies of the chelation reactions are calculated from the relation

$$-\Delta G = RT \ln K^{\mu=0}$$

and are given in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. H.L. Bhatnagar, Head of the Chemistry Department, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra for providing laboratory facilities and one of them (BCB) is also thankful to the UGC for providing a fellowship.

References

1. H. J. LAJUNEN, *Lauri Minn. Chem. Lett.*, 1976, **3**, 53.
2. N. S. POLUEKTOV, L. A. ALAKAEVA, M. A. TISCHENKO, *Russian J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **18**, 40.
3. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003.
4. J. BJERRUM, Metal amine formation in aqueous solution, (P. Haase and Son, Copenhagen), 1941.
5. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
6. G. B. WENGERT, R. C. WALKER and V. A. STENGER, *Analyt. Chem.*, 1952, **24**, 1936.
7. S. N. DUBEY, A. SINGH, H. L. KALRA and D. M. PURI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 451.
8. S. CHABREK and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 5032.
9. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
10. S. N. DUBEY and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 327.
11. T. MOELLER, *Chemistry of Lanthanides*, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1970, 31.